

Pan-European Soil Type Classification: Embeddings vs Environmental Covariates

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Abstract

Accurate continental-scale soil-type mapping requires models that can generalize across heterogeneous pedoclimatic settings while exploiting increasingly rich Earth observation data. This study evaluates whether AlphaEarth Foundations embeddings improve pan-European World Reference Base (WRB) soil-type classification relative to conventional environmental covariates. More than 20,000 harmonized soil observations covering 186 WRB classes were linked to approximately 100 climatic, terrain, lithological, vegetation, moisture, and gridded soil covariates, together with 64-dimensional AlphaEarth embeddings. Explainable Boosting Machine classifiers were trained using embeddings only, environmental covariates only, and their combination, with Bayesian hyperparameter tuning and spatially blocked validation. Environmental covariates achieved the highest accuracy (0.28; macro F1 = 0.21), while the combined model performed similarly and embeddings alone were weaker (0.21; macro F1 = 0.13). Results indicate that current embeddings largely duplicate broad climatic and terrain signals rather than adding independent information for detailed WRB classification.

Keywords: soil type classification; AlphaEarth embeddings; geospatial foundation models; Explainable Boosting Machine; World Reference Base

1. Introduction

Soil types and soil classification synthesize pedogenic processes, landform relationships, and diagnostic horizons into a compact description of soil functioning, making them directly relevant to soil health assessment, crop yield modeling, land use planning, and environmental policy. Yet conventional soil survey and polygon-based mapping are widely viewed as too slow and resource-intensive to provide timely, high-detail soil type information at continental scale, which has accelerated interest in machine-learning (ML) approaches that link legacy soil observations to environ-

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mental covariates (Hengl et al. 2025).

Methodologically, most soil-type ML workflows rely on environmental covariates and derived indices that embed task-specific assumptions about which surface signals proxy soil-forming conditions (Wadoux, Minasny, and McBratney 2020; Manteghi et al. 2024; Hounkpatin et al. 2018). These features often embed domain knowledge, but can constrain model transferability between regions, land-use contexts, and different remote sensing platforms. In contrast, geospatial foundation-model embeddings, such as AlphaEarth (Brown et al. 2025), aim to provide general-purpose representations that compress multi-sensor spatiotemporal information into latent geospatial semantics, potentially reducing manual feature engineering while improving spatial generalization for downstream mapping tasks.

Motivated by these gaps, this study compares soil-type classification based on AlphaEarth embeddings with a strong baseline built from environmental covariates, as well as a model that combines both. We use a harmonized, pan-European point dataset of World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB) soil types and a multiscale set of environmental covariates that reflects current best practice in European soil-type mapping.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Data used

The study focuses on pan-European soil-type classification using the WRB classification as the target legend. Training labels come from a harmonized compilation of legacy soil profiles assembled by OpenGeoHub Foundation, standardized to World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB) classes using correlation/cross-walking procedures. After filtering rare classes, the modeling dataset contains over 20,000 records across 186 soil-type classes. Observation-level quality codes are used to account for differences in label reliability (e.g., original WRB vs converted legends vs imputed qualifiers). See Minarik et al. (2024) for more details.

Each point was linked to an environmental predictor stack of approximately 100 variables with a resolution of 30 m to 1 km, capturing broad controls on soil formation and near-surface conditions. The predictors represent climatic gradients (Karger et al. 2021; Brun et al. 2022), terrain and hydrological setting across multiple spatial scales (Ho et al. 2025), lithological/parent-material information (Isik, Minarik, and Hengl 2024), vegetation and land-surface reflectance signals, moisture-related proxies (Hengl 2025), and gridded soil information layers (e.g., soil organic carbon and pH).

AlphaEarth Foundations embeddings are precomputed, 64-dimensional satellite embedding vectors that compress multi-sensor Earth observation time series into an analysis-ready representation of local landscape context for each pixel/year (Brown et al. 2025). For the embedding-based classification, each soil observation is linked to AlphaEarth vectors extracted for the year 2024. Embeddings are treated as fixed-length latent descriptors of local landscape context and are sampled at the soil point locations.

2.2. Soil type classification with Explainable Boosting Machine

We performed soil type classification using the Explainable Boosting Machine (EBM) (Nori et al. 2019), an interpretable “glassbox” machine learning approach based on additive models that capture non-linear feature–response relationships and, where enabled, selected pairwise interactions. Model hyperparameters were optimized with Bayesian tuning while using spatially blocked cross-validation to reduce inflation of performance estimates due to spatial autocorrelation and to better reflect spatial generalization.

We trained and evaluated three EBM-based soil-type classifiers using AlphaEarth Foundations (AEF) embeddings only, environmental covariates only, and the combined feature set (AEF + environmental covariates). Each model was tuned independently with Optuna using Bayesian hyperparameter optimization and assessed under the same spatial validation design (Akiba et al. 2019).

3. Results and Discussion

In all runs, the model with environmental-covariates-only and the combined model achieved nearly identical performance, with overall accuracy in the 27–28% range. The AEF-only model consistently yielded the lowest accuracy among the three configurations. In general, the addition of AEF embeddings to the environmental covariates did not produce a measurable gain in precision relative to the use of environmental covariates alone, while the use of embeddings in isolation resulted in a clearly weaker classification performance (21% classification accuracy) (see Table 1).

The feature importance comparison across the three EBM models highlights the dominant role of macro-climatic and terrain covariates in WRB Reference Soil Group classification at continental scale (see Fig.1). In the environmental-covariates-only model, importance is concentrated on macro-climatic and terrain-derived covariates. The AEF-only model shows an importance largely assigned to the embeddings A50 and A26. In the combined model, importance is redistributed across both feature sets, retaining BIO4 at the top while reintroducing key AEF embedding layers, A26 and A50. The feature importance is flatter and more evenly distributed, with lower individual values but more features contributing meaningfully. This harmonious spread is the strength of EBM’s additive and low-greed boosting design, which fairly allocates the feature importance across correlated features instead of letting a few dominate as in traditional tree ensembles. AlphaEarth embeddings overlap substantially with climate, radiation, and moisture variables because the model is trained on a multimodal dataset that explicitly includes climate reanalysis data. This pattern in the feature distribution indicates substantial overlap between multispectral embeddings and direct environmental drivers, suggesting that broad climatic envelopes remain the primary signal to distinguish soil types on the continental scale, with limited additional value from the embeddings once environmental data are included.

These findings suggest that most of the predictive signal exploited by EBM is already captured by the environmental covariates, whereas the additional information contained in single-year AEF embeddings may be redundant. This redundancy may limit spatial generalization because the embeddings appear to encode broad environmental gradients more strongly than diagnostic soil-forming properties that distinguish closely related WRB classes. Nonetheless, they may still be

Table 1: Macro-averaged metrics for validation of EBM models using independent testing set.

Feature set	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
AEF embeddings only	0.21	0.18	0.14	0.13
Environmental covariates only	0.28	0.26	0.21	0.21
Combined (AEF + environmental)	0.27	0.24	0.20	0.20

valuable in specific soil or landscape contexts where surface expression, vegetation dynamics, hydrological conditions, or land-use history provide diagnostic information not fully represented by conventional covariates.

Further experiments are needed to clarify the conditions under which embeddings may add independent value, including multi-year embedding aggregation, alternative foundation-model representations, task-specific adaptation strategies, and class- or region-specific analyses.

Figure 1: Feature importance in three EBM models (left to right): AEF-only, Environmental covariates only, and AEF + Environmental combined.

4. Conclusion

This study compared AlphaEarth Foundations embeddings, conventional environmental covariates, and their combination for pan-European WRB soil-type classification using Explainable Boosting Machine models. The results show that environmental covariates remain the strongest predictor set, achieving slightly higher performance than the combined model, while the embedding-only model performed substantially worse. Adding AlphaEarth embeddings did not improve classification accuracy, suggesting that the embeddings largely capture information already represented by climate, terrain, moisture, and other environmental variables. These findings indicate that, for detailed continental-scale soil-type classification, current geospatial embeddings should be viewed as complementary descriptors rather than replacements for physically interpretable environmental covariates. In future work, we will test multi-year embedding aggregation, alternative foundation-model representations, and class- or region-specific analyses to better identify where embeddings may provide independent value.

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References

- Akiba, Takuya, Shotaro Sano, Toshihiko Yanase, Takeru Ohta, and Masanori Koyama. 2019. “Optuna: A Next-generation Hyperparameter Optimization Framework.” In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*.
- Brown, Christopher F., Michal R. Kazmierski, Valerie J. Pasquarella, William J. Rucklidge, Masha Samsikova, Chenhui Zhang, Evan Shelhamer, et al. 2025. *AlphaEarth Foundations: An embedding field model for accurate and efficient global mapping from sparse label data*. arXiv: 2507.22291 [cs.CV]. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.22291>.
- Brun, P., N. E. Zimmermann, C. Hari, L. Pellissier, and D. N. Karger. 2022. *CHELSEA-BIOCLIM+: A novel set of global climate-related predictors at kilometre-resolution*. *EnviDat*. <https://doi.org/10.16904/envidat.332>.
- Hengl, T., D. Consoli, X. Tian, T. W. Nauman, M. Nussbaum, M. S. Isik, L. Parente, et al. 2025. “OpenLandMap-soildb: global soil information at 30 m spatial resolution for 2000–2022+ based on spatiotemporal Machine Learning and harmonized legacy soil samples and observations.” *Earth System Science Data Discussions* 2025:1–66. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-336>. <https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2025-336/>.
- Hengl, Tomislav. 2025. *Surface soil moisture for Europe 2014–2024 at 1 km annual and quarterly aggregates*. Version V1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14833053>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14833053>.

- Ho, Yu-Feng, Carlos H. Grohmann, John Lindsay, Hannes I. Reuter, Leandro Parente, Martijn Witjes, and Tomislav Hengl. 2025. "GEDTM30: global ensemble digital terrain model at 30 m and derived multiscale terrain variables." *PeerJ* 13 (July): e19673. ISSN: 2167-8359. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.19673>.
- Hounkpatin, Kpade O. L., Karsten Schmidt, Felix Stumpf, Gerald Forkuor, Thorsten Behrens, Thomas Scholten, Wulf Amelung, and Gerhard Welp. 2018. "Predicting reference soil groups using legacy data: A data pruning and Random Forest approach for tropical environment (Dano catchment, Burkina Faso)." *Scientific Reports* 8:9959. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-28244-w>.
- Isik, Mustafa Serkan, Robert Minarik, and T. Hengl. 2024. *Continental Europe surface lithology based on EGDI / OneGeology map at 1:1M scale*. V. V2. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.12607973, July. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12607973>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12607973>.
- Karger, D.N., O. Conrad, J. Boehner, T. Kawohl, H. Kreft, R.W. Soria-Auza, N.E. Zimmermann, H.P. Linder, and M. Kessler. 2021. *Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas*. EnviDat. <https://doi.org/10.16904/envidat.228.v2.1>.
- Manteghi, Shaho, Kamran Moravej, Seyed Roohollah Mousavi, Mohammad Amir Delavar, and Andrea Mastinu. 2024. "Digital soil mapping for soil types using machine learning approaches at the landscape scale in the arid regions of Iran." *Advances in Space Research* 74 (1): 1–16. ISSN: 0273-1177. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2024.04.042>. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0273117724003892>.
- Minarik, Robert, Tomislav Hengl, Rolf Simoes, Mustafa Serkan Isik, Yu-Feng Ho, and Xuemeng Tian. 2024. *Soil type (World Reference Base) map of Europe based on Ensemble Machine Learning and multiscale EO data*. PREPRINT (Version 1). Available at Research Square, October. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5244083/v1>. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5244083/v1>.
- Nori, Harsha, Samuel Jenkins, Paul Koch, and Rich Caruana. 2019. "Interpretml: A unified framework for machine learning interpretability." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.09223*.
- Wadoux, Alexandre M. J.-C., Budiman Minasny, and Alex B. McBratney. 2020. "Machine learning for digital soil mapping: Applications, challenges and suggested solutions." *Earth-Science Reviews* 210:103359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103359>.